

Online Home Services

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Abstract:- The Online Home Service System is a modern technological solution designed to streamline and enhance the delivery of various household services to homeowners and residents. The system offers a user-friendly web and mobile application interface that allows homeowners to easily request a wide range of services, including plumbing, electrical repairs, house cleaning, gardening, appliance maintenance, and more. Service providers, ranging from independent contractors to established companies, can register on the platform to offer their expertise, expand their customer base, and optimize their scheduling and resource management. This abstract provides a concise overview of the key components and benefits of the Online Home Service System.

Keywords:- Service Booking System, Household Maintenance, Service Scheduling, User-Friendly Interface.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Online Home Service System is a web and mobile-based platform that has redefined the way individuals manage household maintenance, repairs, and improvements. This cutting-edge system leverages digital technologies to connect homeowners with an extensive network of service professionals, creating a seamless and efficient way to address a wide range of domestic needs. The driving force behind this system is the growing demand for hassle-free access to a variety of services, including plumbing, electrical repairs, house cleaning, gardening, appliance maintenance, and much more.

A. Problems faced during selecting a project:

Market Research and Demand Assessment: Identifying the specific services that homeowners require can be challenging. It's essential to conduct comprehensive market research to understand the local demand, competition, and consumer preferences.

- **Technology Selection:** Choosing the right technology stack and infrastructure for your online home service platform can be a complex decision. It's important to select technologies that are scalable, secure, and capable of providing a seamless user experience.
- **Service Provider Network:** Building a network of reliable service providers is a crucial but often challenging task. Recruiting skilled professionals and ensuring their qualifications and credibility can be time-consuming.
- **User Interface and User Experience:** Designing an intuitive and user-friendly interface is paramount. Failing to do so can result in a poor user experience, leading to dissatisfaction and low user retention.

B. Challenges faced by Student during project selection:

- **Market Research:** Conducting comprehensive market research to understand the specific needs and demands of homeowners in a particular region or demographic group can be time-consuming. Without a clear understanding of the market, students may struggle to identify a viable project idea.
- **Technical Expertise:** Building an online home service system requires technical expertise in web development and database management. Without a strong technical background may find it challenging to implement the project vision.
- **Technical Challenges:** Integrating features like real-time scheduling, payment processing, geolocation services, and user authentication can present technical hurdles. We may need to learn new technologies and overcome technical obstacles.
- **Time Management:** Project timelines and deadlines can be demanding. We must effectively manage the time to complete the project within the allotted time.
- **Feedback and Iteration:** Receiving feedback from users and making iterative improvements to the project can be a challenge. We should be prepared to adapt the system based on user feedback and changing needs.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The most important step in the web development process is the literature review. This will describe some preliminary research that was carried out by several authors on this appropriate work and we are going to take some important articles into consideration and further extend our work.

- Madhavi Mali, Harshal Mahajan, Harsh Deogadkar, Vedant Mahajan, Parth Biradar, proposed a research article, "Survey on Online Home Service System". In this article, the author try to develop a web domain that users can request for home service and the company can give several tasks to the workers which was order by the user. Our website saves time of user because service is provided fast and each service in affordable charges to user.
- Indravan, Adarsh, Shruthi, Shanthi, Dadapeer, proposed a research article, "An Online System for Household Services". In this article, the author try to provide an authenticated and authorized login module for the users such as service seekers, service providers and the admin, by providing appropriate credentials at the time of registration.
- Nikam Poonam R, Gunjal Trupti T, Jadhav Priti V, Parakhe Sonali K, Ms. Prachi S, proposed a research article, "Survey on Home Service Provider". In this article, the author try to provide real-time tracking of technician based on geo-location to provide faster

service.

- Er.Swati Gurav, Shaikh Aswad, Khan Safiullah , Nagrale Mansi, ,proposed a research article,” Doorstep home services”. In this article,the author try to provide the help would be provided with minimal user’s interaction as the only thing the user would have to do is book a time slot for the appropriate skilled personal.
- Ms. Prachi S. Tambe , Nikam Poonam, Gunjal Trupti , Jadhav Priti , Parakhe Sonali, proposed a research article,” An Online System for Home Services ”.In this article,the author try to design anddevelop a system that provides variety of services like plumbers, movers and packers, repair persons services at your doorstep in just one click.
- Amruta Amol Bhawarathi , Kaustubh Muley , Kavya Amrutkar , Devendra Kawade , Anushka Kausadikar , Ayush Kawane , Kaustubh Singh, proposed a research article, “ Website for Home Service Provider”. In this article,the main motive of this system is to serve customers at their doorstep according to their requirements. It offers a one-stop solution for all home-related needs, including repair, cleaning, appliance installation, renovation, and many more. Our team consists of skilled and experienced professionals who are dedicated to providing top-notch services at an affordable price.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In our website, we provide user to register and then login to the page so that user can reach the servicesbased on their requirement and we provide variety of services in the application. Our website provides the gadgets based on the service the user wants and which is price affordable.

A. *Principal features of the proposed work could include:*

- **Database:** sqlLite3 which stores the data of the user who register for the required service.
- **User Interface:** Our system provides user friendly interface. Frontend is designed by using html, CSS, bootstrap.
- **Framework:** Django makes the development of web applications much easier using python. It providessecurity and database connectivity.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 1: Home Page

- **Explanation:** From the above window we can see the home page which offers services for the user.

Fig. 2: Types of Services Explanation:

From the above window the user the types are services are given.

Fig. 3: Get Started

- **Explanation:** From the above window the user can get started to book the service.

Fig. 4: Available Services

- **Explanation:** From the above window we can see the home page which offers the types of services.

Fig. 5: Available sub-services

- **Explanation:** From the above window the user can select the service and know the cost of the service according to their requirements.

Fig. 6: Services Cost

- **Explanation:** From the above window we can see the home page which offers the types in Applicationservices.

Fig. 7: AC Services

- **Explanation:** From the above window we can see the home page which offers the types in Ac services.

Fig. 8: Home Need Services

- **Explanation:** From the above window we can see the home page which offers the types in Home Needsservices.

Fig. 9: Register Form

- **Explanation:** From the above window the user can register to the service needed.

Fig. 10: Request saved successfully

- **Explanation:** From the above window the user request for their service order has been placed successfully.

Fig. 11: FeedBack Form

- **Explanation:** From the above window the user can submit a feedback to the admin so that they can improve the website.

V. CONCLUSION

In our web application, it provides the services which is cost affordable based on service and the user can easily communicate to the service provider if there is any issue.

After booking the service the user will get an mail that is service they need is successful or not.

The user can easily book the service without any issues and it is convenient to book an online service otherwise it takes to time to get an service and make it done.

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